

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF COMMINGLED CF/PEEK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The static and fatigue properties of continuous AS4 carbon fibre (CF) reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite laminates made from commingled unifabric prepreg were investigated under static tension and tension-tension fatigue loading. Three different lay-ups were studied, namely $[0]_{16}$, $[90]_{16}$ and $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$. The results for static stiffness and strength as well as fatigue life and residual strength under different fatigue stress amplitudes were evaluated, and the damage and failure mechanisms of the composite laminates were discussed. The wear-out model was applied to fit the S-N curves and estimate residual strength of composite laminates, and good correlation was obtained. Compared to composite laminates made from pre-impregnated tape prepreg (e.g. APC-2), the commingled CF/PEEK composite laminates are more sensitive to fatigue loading because of imperfect fibre bundle alignment.

KEYWORDS: fatigue behaviour, CF/PEEK composites, commingled prepreg, tension-tension fatigue, damage mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue behaviour of a composite structure is an important property for engineering applications. For many years the primary matrix materials used in polymer-based composites have been thermosets. High performance thermoplastics have been introduced as matrix materials in recent years, which have many advantages over their thermosetting counterparts. In particular, thermoplastic matrices offer the potential for simpler, less time-consuming manufacturing cycles [1,2]. Continuous carbon fibre (CF) reinforced polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) composites constitute one group of the most competitive materials in the aerospace and defence industries. CF/PEEK prepreg is usually supplied in a form of pre-impregnated tapes (e.g. APC-2). However, more recently CF/PEEK prepreg has been available in form of a woven fabric, consisting of unidirectional and continuous carbon fibres mingled with continuous PEEK fibres, which are interwoven with continuous PEEK fibres in the transverse direction. This type of prepreg is particularly suitable for manufacturing components of complex geometry. The fatigue behaviour of CF/PEEK composites produced from this type of prepreg has not been studied comprehensively. The main objectives of this work are to investigate the static and fatigue properties of commingled unifabric CF/PEEK composite laminates under static tension and tension-tension fatigue loading and to compare them with those of continuous CF/PEEK composite laminates made from the pre-impregnated tape prepreg (e.g. APC-1, APC-2). The damage and failure mechanisms in the composite laminates are discussed and the fatigue performance of the laminates is evaluated using the wear-out model.

MATERIAL PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was commingled continuous carbon fibre reinforced PEEK unifabric (UD AS4 3K/PEEK) supplied by the Polymer Research Division, BASF. A diagram of the commingled unifabric system is shown in Fig. 1. The diameter of PEEK fibres is approximately 130 μm in the cross-weave and 30 μm in the longitudinal direction, where PEEK fibres were mingled with carbon fibres. The global weight percentage of PEEK polymer in the preform is 32%. With a density of 1.265 g/cm^3 for non-crystallised PEEK [3], the fibre volume fraction amounts to 55% in a fully consolidated composite.

Fig. 1 Schematics of commingled CF/PEEK composite unifabric prepreg.

Fig. 2 Processing cycle of CF/PEEK laminates from commingled unifabric prepreg.

Unidirectional prepreg layers were produced through “edge-welding” the unifabric with a soldering iron into 199×199 mm sheets, with subsequent cutting. The prepreg layers were then placed in a steel mould of a 200×200 mm square cavity in specified stacking sequences and consolidated using a laboratory hot press. Two different lay-ups were chosen in manufacturing the panels, i.e. unidirectional $[0]_{16}$ and $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$. The 16 layers of prepreg gave a subsequent panel thickness of approximate 2.2 mm after consolidation. Upilex® polyimide films (50 μm in thickness) coated with Frekote®-FRP release agent were used between the prepreg stack and the mould surface to ensure easy removal of the panels after consolidation. The processing cycles of the composite laminates are outlined in Fig. 2.

Two different geometries of specimens were chosen, i.e. “straight-side” for static tests and “dog-bone shape” for fatigue tests, shown in Fig. 3. The specimens were end-tabbed for

testing, bonding aluminium tabs of 40 mm in length and 2 mm in thickness with a CIBA-GEIGY Araldite superstrength adhesive.

Fig. 3 Geometrical dimensions of coupon specimens.

The static tensile tests were performed using Instrons 1195 and 5567 respectively at a constant cross-head rate of 1.0 mm/min. A clip gauge with a gauge length of 25 mm was attached to the middle part of specimens during testing to measure the strain response and consequently determine the stiffness. The fatigue tests were conducted on an Instron 8501 hydraulic serve machine under load control at a frequency of 8 Hz with a stress ratio of 0.1. Some tests were continued until the specimen failed in order to establish S-N curves, the rest tests were terminated at specified stages of fatigue life for measurements of residual-tensile stiffness and strength as well as investigations of damage mechanisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Properties

From the stress-strain response, the static strength and stiffness of laminates with three different lay-ups are determined, listed in Table 1, which are compared with the corresponding properties of XAS/PEEK (APC-1, $V_f=55\%$) [4], AS4/PEEK (APC-2, $V_f=60\%$) [1] and AS4/Epoxy ($V_f=68\%$) [5] laminates as well as those of a pure PEEK resin [3] in Fig. 4. The longitudinal tensile strength of the CF/PEEK commingled unidirectional composite laminate is 17% higher than that of APC-1 composite which is of the same fibre volume fraction as the former, but is clearly lower than those of APC-2 and AS4/Epoxy composites because these are of higher fibre volume fractions. In principle, the longitudinal tensile strength of the CF/PEEK commingled composite laminates should be lower than that of composites of the same fibre volume fraction made from the pre-impregnated tape prepreg, because in the former the fibres are not stretched out as in the latter so that the fibre reinforcement is not as effective as in the latter. However, the reason why the CF/PEEK commingled composite is of higher static tensile strength than APC-1 is probably due to the fact that the strength of AS4 fibres is about 16% higher than that of XAS fibres [6]. The longitudinal stiffness of the CF/PEEK commingled composite is about 10% lower than those of APC-2 and AS4/Epoxy because of higher fibre volume fractions in both composites.

The average transverse tensile strength of the CF/PEEK commingled composite is almost the same to that of APC-2 [1] but is 28% higher than that of AS4/Epoxy composites, indicating that the failure strength of unidirectional composites under transverse tension is controlled by the matrix strength. The transverse strengths of all PEEK matrix composites are lower than that of the pure PEEK resin as shown in Fig. 6. Unlike the longitudinal tensile strength which is determined almost entirely by the fibre strength, the transverse tensile strength is governed by many factors including properties of the fibre and matrix, the interface bond strength, the presence and distribution of voids, the residual stress and interactions between these mechanisms. The transverse stiffnesses of CF/PEEK, APC-2 and AS4/Epoxy are quite close to each other, and they are all much higher than that of the pure PEEK resin.

Fig. 4. Static strength (a) and stiffness (b) of CF/PEEK commingled laminates in comparison with those of other composite materials.

Table 1 Properties of commingled CF/PEEK composite laminates

Lay-up	Strength σ_o		Stiffness E_o		Ultimate Strain	
	Mean [MPa]	CV[%]	Mean [MPa]	CV[%]	Mean [MPa]	CV[%]
[0] ₁₆	1507.05	7.20	124.57	3.43	1.17	17.20
[90] ₁₆	88.61	9.58	9.03	1.56	1.31	7.57
[0 ₂ /90 ₂] _{2S}	744.17	8.87	68.27	4.73	1.18	6.15

The static uniaxial strength of the CF/PEEK [0₂/90₂]_{2S} cross-ply laminate is very close to that of APC-1 [7] laminate with 11 plies (six in the axial direction and five in the transverse direction) because of the higher strength of AS4 fibres although a [0₂/90₂]_{2S} laminate contains a less percentage of 0° plies. The uniaxial stiffness of CF/PEEK [0₂/90₂]_{2S} laminate is 7% lower than APC-2 and 13% lower than AS4/Epoxy, but about 10% higher than APC-1.

Fatigue Properties

The experimental S-N data for the CF/PEEK composites with three different lay-ups are shown in Figs. 5-7 with comparison with those of unidirectional and cross-ply APC-1 [4] as well as the best fit curve of the pure PEEK resin [3], respectively. Compared with APC-1,

the S-N data of the unidirectional CF/PEEK commingled composite exhibit quicker degradation in Fig. 4, indicating that this material is more fatigue sensitive.

Fig. 5 S-N curve of unidirectional $[0]_{16}$ CF/PEEK laminate (\diamond : static data, \blacklozenge : fatigue data) in comparison with APC-1 (\circ).

Fig. 6 S-N curve of unidirectional $[90]_{16}$ CF/PEEK laminate (\diamond : static data, \blacklozenge : fatigue data) in comparison with PEEK resin.

Fig. 7 S-N curve of cross-ply $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ CF/PEEK laminate (\diamond : static data, \blacklozenge : fatigue data) in comparison with APC-1 (\circ).

The data of cross-ply laminates shown in Fig. 5 exhibit the same trend, and the experimental results of APC-1 cross-ply laminates are almost always above those of CF/PEEK laminates because of a higher percentage of 0° plies. The data of the CF/PEEK $[90]_{16}$ laminates are much more scattered. The best fit curve of S-N data for the pure PEEK resin is above all the data of the CF/PEEK laminates shown in Fig. 6.

Performance Degradation

A series of tests for measurements of residual-tensile stiffness and strength were conducted on the unidirectional $[0]_{16}$ and cross-ply $[0_2,90_2]_{2S}$ CF/PEEK composite laminates which had been fatigued for some specified cycles. The residual strength degradation with cycle number for the CF/PEEK $[0]_{16}$ and $[0_2,90_2]_{2S}$ composite laminates subjected to different fatigue stress levels is plotted in Fig. 8, which exhibit large scatter in experimental data. There is globally little degradation in residual strength during most part of fatigue life for both laminates until the final stage of fatigue damage which causes dramatic degradation in residual strength followed by catastrophic failure of the laminates.

Fig. 8 Residual strength for $[0]_{16}$ unidirectional laminate (a) $\sigma_a=50\%\sigma_o$, (b) $\sigma_a=60\%\sigma_o$ and $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ cross-ply laminate (c) $\sigma_a=60\%\sigma_o$, (d) $\sigma_a=70\%\sigma_o$, ——— wear-out model, o: experimental data.

Failure Mechanisms

Under both static and fatigue loading, fibre breakage is the main micro-damage mode for the unidirectional laminate, which occurs either individually or in the form of bundles as shown in Fig. 9. In the areas where fibres are stretched out, fibres usually break or fragment randomly, while in the areas where fibre bundles are misaligned, fibre bundles fracture occurs because of local stress concentration (Fig. 9b). With the increase of fatigue cycle the fibre bundle fracture occurs continuously. This probably is the reason why the CF/PEEK commingled laminates is much more fatigue sensitive than APC-1. The fibre/matrix interfacial adhesion appeared to be quite good because the isolated and broken fibres are almost never stripped but always coated with the PEEK matrix, shown by the scanning electron microscopy (Fig. 9c).

The $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ cross-ply laminate exhibits multiple damage modes including transverse matrix cracking in the 90° plies in the first stage of damage development and delamination growth along the interfaces between 0° and 90° plies originated from the tips of transverse matrix cracks at the late stage of damage development, and final fibre breakage in 0° plies. Fig. 10 shows the polished edge of a failed specimen under static loading, illustrating transverse matrix cracks and extensive delamination. When the laminate is subjected to fatigue loading, damage usually starts in 90° plies in the form of matrix cracking, which multiplies in number and extends in length with the increase of fatigue cycle. Delamination then initiates at the tips of transverse matrix cracks and propagates through the $0/90$ interface (Fig. 11), causing the continuous load transfer from 90° plies to 0° plies until the massive fibre breakage occurs in 0° plies, which results in the catastrophic failure of the specimen. However, although numerous transverse matrix cracks and large delaminations are observed in the post-failed specimens, the damage in the CF/PEEK composite laminates appears fairly late at the present fatigue stress levels. This phenomenon is different from that of carbon/epoxy laminates [5], in which transverse matrix cracks appear quickly because of brittle characteristics of epoxy resins. In the CF/PEEK composite laminates the tough characteristics of PEEK matrix delay the damage initiation to a late stage of the fatigue life.

Fig. 9 Schematic of misaligned fibre bundle (a), SEM photography of fracture of misaligned bundles (b) and fibre/matrix adhesion (c).

Fig. 10 Photography of the polished edge of a failed $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ specimen under static loading.

Fig. 11 Photography illustrating micro-fracture modes in $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ laminate subjected to cyclic stress $\sigma_a=60\%\sigma_o$ for $N=684,000$ cycles

WEAR-OUT MODEL ANALYSIS

To evaluate the fatigue behaviour of the CF/PEEK laminates of different lay-ups, the wear-out model of residual strength proposed by Halpin et al. [8] is applied. The degradation of residual strength of composites under fatigue loading is assumed to be in the form of

$$\sigma_r^\gamma = \sigma_o^\gamma - A\sigma_a^\gamma(N-1) \quad (1)$$

where σ_r , σ_o , σ_a are the residual strength, the static strength and the maximum applied cyclic stress, respectively, γ and A are material constants to be determined. This equation means that the strength of a composite laminate decreases from the initial value σ_o to σ_r after N cycles of fatigue loading with the maximum cyclic stress σ_a . When the residual strength equals to the maximum applied stress, i.e. $\sigma_r=\sigma_a$, Eq. (1) is reduced to the S-N relation of the laminate,

$$\sigma_e = \sigma_a [1 + A(N-1)]^S, \quad S = \frac{1}{\gamma} \quad (2)$$

where σ_e is the equivalent static strength. The formulation of the wear-out model is completed assuming that the equivalent static strength obeys a two-parameter Weibull distribution, and the probability of the static strength higher than σ_e , or the reliability, is given by

$$P(\sigma_e) = \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{\sigma_e}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right\} \quad (3)$$

where α and β are the Weibull shape and scale parameters, respectively. To evaluate fatigue behaviour of composite laminates, these four parameters γ , A , α and β can be determined, fitting the wear-out model to the experimental data.

The model parameters, calculated with the maximum likelihood method [9, 10], are obtained for the CF/PEEK laminates of three different lay-ups, listed in Table 2. The S-N curve of each composite laminate calculated from Eq. (2), with the equivalent static strength determined by

$\sigma_e = \beta \Gamma (1 + 1/\alpha)$, is shown as a solid line in Figs. 5-7, respectively. The dashed lines denote the 95% confidence level. It can be seen that the wear-out model provides a good estimation to the experimental data.

Table 2. Parameters of fatigue model for CF/PEEK commingled composite laminates.

Lay-up	S	A	α	β [MPa]
[0] ₁₆	0.0630	0.1117	21.80	1549.25
[90] ₁₆	0.0237	0.0629	8.78	88.19
[0 ₂ /90 ₂] _{2S}	0.0604	0.0409	17.69	769.66

The residual strength degradation behaviour is simulated for both unidirectional [0]₁₆ and cross-ply laminates [0₂/90₂]_{2S} at different fatigue stress levels using the model parameters in Table 2, which is shown as a solid line in Fig. 8. The difference between the wear-out model and experimental data for the [0]₁₆ laminate at a fatigue stress level of 50% static strength is clearly visible. While for other stress levels, the wear-out model is correlated with the experimental data very well for both [0]₁₆ and [0₂/90₂]_{2S} laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the present study, the following points can be highlighted:

1. The static properties of the CF/PEEK composite laminates made from commingled unifabric prepreg are higher than those of APC-1 because of the higher tensile strength of AS4 fibres, but are clearly lower than those of APC-2 due to a lower fibre volume fraction.
2. The composite laminates exhibit higher fatigue sensitivity under tension-tension fatigue loading than APC-1 because of fibre bundle breakage at the locations where fibre bundles are misaligned.
3. The matrix cracking in transverse plies and extensive delaminations between 0° and 90° plies initiated from the tips of transverse matrix cracks are two main damage mechanisms in the cross-ply laminate. Compared with carbon/epoxy composite laminates, the damage in the CF/PEEK laminates appears relatively late, because the tough characteristics of the matrix delay the initiation of damage.
4. The wear-out model shows good correlation with the experimental data for both S-N curve and residual strength.

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